

Letter to the Editor

On Syntropy & Precognitive Interdiction Based on Wheeler-Feynman's Absorber Theory

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ABSTRACT

It has been known for long time that intuition plays significant role in many professions and human life, including in entrepreneurship, government, and also in detective or law enforcement activities. Women are known to possess better intuitive feelings or “hunch” compared to men. Despite these examples, such a precognitive interdiction is hardly accepted in established science. In this letter, we discuss briefly the advanced solutions of Maxwell equations, and then explore plausible connection between syntropy and precognition.

Keywords: Intuition, syntropy, precognition, Maxwell equation, advanced wave solution.

1. Introduction

It has been known for long time that intuition plays significant role in many professions and other aspects of human life, including in entrepreneurship, government, and also in detective or law enforcement activities. Even women are known to possess better intuitive feelings or “*hunch*” compared to men¹. Despite these examples, such a precognitive interdiction is hardly accepted in established science.

In this paper, we discuss briefly the advanced solutions of Maxwell equations in the context of Wheeler-Feynman-Cramer's absorber theory, and then make connection between *syntropy* and precognition from classical perspective. This may be regarded as first step to describe such precognition activities which are usually considered belong to quantum realm.

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¹ This paper is inspired in part by our discussion few months ago with Dr. Carmen Wrede from Germany. She told that she got a *hunch* or a feeling to experience electromagnetic wave from certain future events.

It is our hope that the new proposed interpretation can be verified with experimental data. Nonetheless, we admit that our model is still in its infancy, more researches are needed to fill all the missing details.

2. John Cramer's take on Wheeler-Feynman's absorber theory

The Wheeler-Feynman's paper on absorber theory has been discussed and generalized by John Cramer. He discussed among other things on the physical interpretation of advanced and retarded solutions of Maxwell equations and also Klein-Gordon equation.

Our discussion starts from the fundamental Maxwell's equations that unify electromagnetism[1]:

$$\begin{aligned}\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} &= 0 (\text{Magnetic Gauss}), \\ \nabla \cdot \mathbf{D} &= \rho_f (\text{Gauss}), \\ \nabla \times \mathbf{E} + \partial_t \mathbf{B} &= 0 (\text{Faraday}), \\ \nabla \times \mathbf{H} - \partial_t \mathbf{D} &= \mathbf{J}_f (\text{Ampere circuit law}),\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

It is known that electromagnetic wave equation corresponding to (1) admits advanced wave solution.

Of course, here we do not have to accept all transactional QM interpretation by Cramer[1][2], but we can keep our discussion straightly within the scope of classical electromagnetic theory.

The electromagnetic wave equation for source-free space can be written in the form:

$$c^2 \nabla^2 \vec{F} = \frac{d^2 \vec{F}}{dt^2},\tag{2}$$

where c represents the speed of light, and F represents either the electric field vector E or the magnetic field vector B of the wave [1].

Since this differential equation is second order in both time and space, it has two independent time solutions and two independent space solutions. Let us restrict our consideration to one dimension by requiring that the wave motion described by equation (2) moves along with x axis and that the E vector of the wave is along the y axis.

Then two independent time solutions of equation (2) might have the form [1]:

$$\vec{E}_{\pm}(x, t) = \hat{y} E_0 \sin \left[2\pi \left(\frac{x}{\lambda} \pm ft \right) \right],\tag{3}$$

and

$$\vec{B}_{\pm}(x,t) = \hat{y}B_0 \sin\left[2\pi\left(\frac{x}{\lambda} \pm ft\right)\right], \quad (4)$$

Quoting from Cramer's notes on the solutions of equations (3) and (4) [1] :

Thus, wave $E_+(x,t)$ is a *negative-energy* (and *negative-frequency*) solution of Eq. (1). As mentioned above, it will arrive at a point a distance x from the source at a time $t = x/c$. *before* the instant of emission. For this reason, it is called an *advanced* wave. Solution $E_-(x,t)$, on the other hand, is the more familiar positive-energy solution of Eq. (1). It arrives at x a time $t = x/c$ after the instant of emission and is called the *retarded* solution.

It should be clear, therefore, that advanced wave solution is inherent in the classical electromagnetic wave equations, without having to resort to Cramer's transactional interpretation of QM.

Next, we are going to discuss physical interpretation of such an advanced wave solution.

3. Interpretation of Advanced Wave Solution: Syntropy and Precognition

The above analysis by Cramer which seems to suggest that EPR paradox just disappears when considering the advanced waves to be real physical entities, has been suggested by other physicists too, notably: Costa de Beauregard and also Luigi Fantappie. While working on quantum mechanics and special relativity equations, Luigi noted that that retarded waves (retarded potentials) are governed by the law of entropy, while the advanced waves are governed by a symmetrical law that he named "*syntropy*"[3].

Therefore, some psychologists who work in this area began to make connection between the notion of syntropy and precognitive interdiction. And recently, a new journal by title *Syntropy* has been started to facilitate such a discussion.

But again let us emphasize here that equation (3) and (4) indicate that the advanced wave solutions have purely classical origin. Therefore, we do not discuss yet their connection with other alleged QM terminologies such as collapsing wave function which are hardly possible to prove experimentally, despite Bohr and Heisenberg insisted such a phenomenon is real. This is our departure to QM's inspired syntropy discussions in [3]-[6].

Our knowledge in this area is very limited, but we can expect that research in this direction of precognitive interdiction will flourish in the near future, once we can accept that it is purely classical origin, so we do not have to invoke complicated QM arguments.

As a last remark for experimenters, it may be advisable to verify this syntropy effect in women, especially those who have already proved themselves as good ‘*precogniters*.’”

4. Conclusion

It has been known for long time that intuition plays significant role in many professions and various aspects of human life, including in entrepreneurship, government, and also in detective or law enforcement activities. Even women are known to possess better intuitive feelings or “*hunch*” compared to men.

Despite these examples, such a precognitive interdiction or hunch (gut feeling) is hardly accepted in established science. In this paper, we discuss briefly the advanced solutions of Maxwell equations, and then make connection between syntropy and precognition from classical perspective. This may be regarded as first step to describe such precognition activities which are usually considered belong to quantum realm.

But we admit that our model is still in its infancy, more researches are needed to fill all the missing details. Further observations and experiments are recommended to verify the above propositions.

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